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«GREEN» FUTURE FOR THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

In the past few years, investments in the green economy in the world have been steadily increasing, and the shares of companies focusing on ESG principles have shown steady growth. In this regard, this article analyzes international experience in the implementation of innovative solutions by large energy companies in order to reduce or achieve complete absence of damage to the environment in the process of hydrocarbon production and processing. It is also proposed the production of fuel briquettes from industrial waste as one of the perspective areas on the path to the formation of a «green» economy in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Oil and gas industry, environmental policy, «green» economy, innovative solutions, zero emissions, fuel briquettes, carbon neutrality, alternative fuel

Transitioning the world to a zero-emissions lifestyle is one of the biggest challenges humanity has ever faced. This will require a fundamental change in how we produce, how we consume and how we move. Due to the fact that today the oil and gas industry is the “first” among other sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan in terms of its negative impact on the environment, reducing the intensity of emissions in the production and processing of hydrocarbons remains a strategically important direction for the next 15-20 years. On July 8-9, 2019, the Regional Ministerial Conference of the countries of Europe and the CIS on the "green" economy was held in Tashkent, aimed at improving the regulatory framework and policies for the "green" economy, encouraging innovative "green" investments through partnerships between public and private sectors.

On April 19, 2022, Uzbekistan signed an agreement with the French Development Agency, the purpose of which is to prepare, finance and implement a new strategic mechanism for the "green economy". The main task is to preserve the environment and adapt to climate change. The cooperation is designed for 5 years and the amount of the first loan agreement (150 million euros) will be directed to the development of a program that will facilitate the transition of Uzbekistan to a more efficient model in terms of resources and hydrocarbon emissions. [1]

According to studies, Uzbekistan annually spends at least 4.5% of its GDP due to the use of hydrocarbon energy - oil, gas and coal. However, most of the country's generating capacities are outdated and require huge funds for restoration and modernization. That is why the transition to "green" energy is an economically and environmentally effective solution. [2, 562]

Looking at the activities of regional and global companies, we can see that the leaders of the oil and gas sector are ambitious in planning and setting “Net Zero” targets for greenhouse gas emissions over the 2030-2050 horizon.

Net Zero - carbon neutrality - is a state with zero carbon dioxide emissions. This can be achieved by balancing carbon dioxide emissions with carbon removal (often by offsetting carbon emissions) or by excluding emissions from society. [3, 82]

For example, the Russian multinational energy company «Gazprom» aims to reduce emissions by 30% by 2030. According to the low-carbon development program for 2022-2031, the target for the Kazakh national oil company «KazMunayGas» for 2031 is a 15% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions. The National Oil Company of Saudi Arabia "Saudi Aramco" aims to reduce gas emissions to zero by 2050. [4, 136]

If we consider the actions of global oil and gas companies (Figure 1), we can see that by using renewable energy sources for its own operations, the Norwegian international energy company «Equinor ASA» is going to achieve zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2030. «British Petroleum» plans to launch a pilot project to use green hydrogen to achieve zero emissions by 2050. The largest Italian oil and gas company «Eni S.p.A.» through the use of renewable energy sources for its own operations and the transition to biorefineries, has set itself the goal of reducing emissions by 15% (2035), and by 55% (2050). Spain's largest oil and gas company, Repsol, will gradually reduce its greenhouse gas emissions and thereby reach net zero emissions by 2050 through the production of fuel from waste, as well as the use of a pilot plant for the production of green hydrogen. [5, 62]

Figure 1. Net Zero targets for greenhouse gas emissions over the horizon 2030-2050 developed by global oil and gas leaders [5, 62]

In our country, due to the reduction of natural sources: oil, coal, the problems of waste disposal and the prevention of their negative impact on the environment and directly on the population have become increasingly important in recent years. Processing of industrial and household waste will provide alternative, renewable energy sources. Many developed countries are already solving these problems (Japan, USA, Germany, France). [6, 74] Thus, the processing of consumer waste also brings economic benefits.

In the developed countries of the world, on the basis of efficient technology, the use of industrial and municipal solid waste (MSW), including wood, is practiced as a comparable high-calorie fuel with a lower working calorific value of 5 to 16.5 MJ / kg: in Switzerland 80%, in Denmark, Japan 85%, France 65%, Germany 60%. At present, there are technologies for obtaining fuel pellets and briquettes from wood waste from municipal services and timber industry enterprises and are being applied in practice. It should be noted that one ton of wood briquettes replaces 5 cubic meters of wood, 480 cubic meters of gas, 500 liters of diesel fuel or 700 liters of fuel oil. Fuel briquettes (TB) are not only inferior to traditional types of fuel, but also surpass them in a number of indicators.

For example, the cost of obtaining heat energy from fuel briquettes is lower than coal, lower than heating oil and can compete with natural gas in a number of parameters. They have a high calorific value, comparable to natural traditional sources. When burning, wood briquettes give a stable high and even flame, reaching complete burning within 1-1.5 hours, and in the smoldering mode, high-quality briquettes can give heat for several hours. Ash residue after burning of a briquette does not exceed 1%, while coal has 30-40%. In addition, it is an environmentally friendly, renewable and economic fuel. With heat release comparable to that of classic fuel, carbon dioxide emissions into the air are 10-50 times lower, ash is formed 20 times less, and there is no sulfur content in briquettes. [7, 60]

During long-term storage, briquettes practically do not absorb water, have no smell, unlike standard fuels (gas, diesel fuel, fuel oil), so their high calorific value does not decrease over time, unlike traditional fuels, which depend largely on impurities. When burning a briquette, an efficiency of up to 94% is achieved, and the resulting ash residues can be used as fertilizer by agricultural enterprises. Thus, even now it is possible to replace coal, fuel oil in thermal boiler houses with fuel briquettes as an alternative fuel for generating heat, and burning fuel briquettes on an industrial scale is more profitable than burning coal, fuel oil or gas.

Table 1.

Draft development goals of the ESG JSC "Uzbekneftegaz" by key indicators [8]

Index	Unit of measurement	UNG 2021	Goal	Period
GHG emissions	tons CO ₂ e/thousand tons oil equivalent	198	-25%	2030
Company carbon footprint	million tons CO ₂ e	6,3	0	2050
Emissions of sulfur oxides	tons/thousand tons oil equivalent	2,83	-50%	2030

Uzbekistan also needs to introduce technologies that will help reduce the harm from the development of oil and gas fields. Applying the above-mentioned technology in one of the largest companies in Uzbekistan – JSC «Uzbekneftegaz», will not only ensure the preservation of natural complexes, but also obtain economic benefits and achieve the environmental performance that was planned (Table 1).

Thus, in order for the oil and gas complex of Uzbekistan to switch to the path of a "green economy", it is necessary to modernize the energy industry and update the technological and material base, outdated equipment does not have the ability to efficiently use fuel resources, and leads to environmental pollution. To eliminate such an impact, it is necessary to introduce progressive resource-saving technologies - one of which may be the technology for obtaining fuel pellets, briquettes from wood waste from municipal services and timber industry enterprises. One of the biggest advantages of wood briquettes is that when they are burned, no gas is released that destroys the ozone layer of the atmosphere, and the emission of sulfur is less than 0.05%, which is quite environmentally friendly. Briquettes do not require expensive re-equipment of furnaces and boilers, as it is necessary when burning gas or fuel oil. This technology should pay off in the shortest possible time. Further involvement of other oil and gas companies in solving environmental problems will contribute to the speedy transition of the oil and gas industry of Uzbekistan to a "green economy".

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